

Data Management Plan (DMP) / Plan de Gestión de Datos (PGD)

Integrated analysis of genetic, social, demographic and psychological factors associated to Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in pediatric patients.

Original title: Análisis integrado de factores genéticos, sociodemográficos y psicológicos asociados con el trastorno del espectro autista (TEA) en pacientes pediátricos.

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Funding: Subvenciones para la promoción de proyectos de investigación por el Departamento de Salud 2025, Gobierno de Navarra.

Background: The project proposes an integrative analysis of genetic, social, demographic and psychological factors associated to the Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) for better patient stratification. In order to achieve this, we will design an automated genomic analysis specific for TEA patients, we will run multivariate analysis and perform association studies to identify links and patterns between the factors.

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by persistent deficits in communication skills and social interaction, and restricted and repetitive patterns of behaviour, interests, and activities. These symptoms usually onset in early childhood and interfere with a person's daily life. Because it is a broad spectrum, the manifestations and severity of symptoms vary among individuals.

ASD has a global impact on public health. In recent decades, there has been a significant increase worldwide in the number of children diagnosed with ASD: while in 1931 it only affected 0.001% of the population, in 2021, 1% of children under eight years of age were diagnosed with ASD. According to the WHO, approximately 1 in 100 children worldwide receives an ASD diagnosis. In Spain, the largest study to date, conducted by researchers at Vall d'Hebron Hospital in Barcelona

in 2022, estimates the prevalence at around 1%, slightly higher than that of the European population. These numbers place ASD among the top 10 disorders causing disability in children and adolescents under 20 years of age.

Therefore, although advances in the understanding and treatment of these disorders have been remarkable in recent decades, ASD continues to represent a significant global health and societal challenge.

ASD is considered a complex disorder with a multifactorial etiology in which genetic and environmental factors converge, acting individually or in combination, contributing to the development of the prenatal alterations that cause the disorder. Additionally, social factors surrounding the individual during their development play a fundamental role in the course of ASD.

Genetic factors: Numerous studies suggest that ASD is one of the neurodevelopmental disorders most influenced by genetic factors, with approximately 1,000 genes implicated in susceptibility to ASD.

Environmental factors: A variety of non-genetic factors has been associated in the scientific literature with the risk of ASD, including infections during pregnancy, maternal nutritional and metabolic status, exposure to certain medications, and substance use.

This multifactorial etiology of ASD suggests a liability threshold model (Figure 1) where the condition develops when an individual's cumulative genetic-environmental susceptibility—their total risk—exceeds a certain threshold.

Figure 1. Illustration of the liability threshold model showing the relative weight of different factors in total susceptibility. Cases with multiple low-impact predisposing factors typically go undiagnosed. Huang et al., 2024, Nature.

Social factors: Similarly, multiple social factors can influence detection, diagnosis and access to treatment, thus affecting the likelihood of an early, accurate, and personalized diagnosis and substantially impacting the progression of autism spectrum disorder.

The complex and multifactorial nature of ASD presents a significant challenge in clinical practice, where diagnosis relies on the observation of behavioural symptoms. The contribution from the accumulation of low- and moderate-effect genetic alterations, and their interaction with environmental and social factors, is not assessed. Consequently, valuable information about the mechanisms contributing to the disorder is lost, limiting the ability to personalize interventions and predict clinical course. Furthermore, this behaviour-only approach is particularly inadequate for individuals with “atypical” phenotypes, such as girls and women, ethnic or cultural minorities, or gifted individuals, leading to delayed, incorrect, or missed diagnoses. Without a truly holistic approach, diagnosis will remain reactive and descriptive, rather than preventive, predictive, and personalized.

Hypothesis: ASD is a multifactorial disorder that is determined by both genetic, social, demographic and psychological factors. Taking into account that the genomic analysis of ADS patients is very complex, designing an automated extraction of key genomic variants will improve diagnoses and patient stratification. Further, an integrative analysis will allow to better understanding the causes and the modifying factor of ADS, as well as predisposing factors, following a personalised approach. Thus, we may be able to identify clinically relevant interactions, patterns and markers.

1. Data description

i) Research data from the project NAGENpediatrics. We use genomic data generated using whole genome sequencing analysis (Illumina, DRAGEN) from the cases of ASD of the previously mentioned research project. Such potential secondary use of the data was included in the informed consent signed by every participant of those projects. The corresponding ethical committee has approved this project (Comité de Ética de la Investigación con medicamentos (CEIm, Navarra); Approval code: PI_2025/112).

We re-use whole genome sequencing data of:

- a. NAGENpediatrics – 222 trios / 8 quartets / 1 quintet

In total, we re-use for the analysis data from 703 whole genomes of 301 different cases. These add up for a total of ~500GB of data. We estimate an additional 300GB storage for scripts and outcome files.

ii) Research data from the project IMPaCT-TEA. We integrate sociodemographic data from participants and family:

- a. Age, ethnic origin migratory status, educational and professional level, job status, beneficiaries of financial support schemes.

iii) Research data from the project IMPaCT-TEA. We use clinical data derived from cognitive, intellectual ability and aptitude evaluations from participants and parents of the IMPaCT-TEA project. This data was collected and stored locally for the participants of NAGENpediatrics, adding onto genomic data). This evaluation includes the following tests:

- a) Medical and neuropsychiatric history (family and personal: ASD, ADHD, anxiety, depression, schizophrenia, intellectual disability, autoimmune disorders).
- b) Prenatal and perinatal factors: number of siblings, infections, medications, oxytocin use, type of delivery, obstetric complications (OCS Lewis).
- c) Diagnosis (DSM-5), pharmacological treatment, developmental milestones (psychomotor, language, behavioural).
- d) Psychometric tests: WAIS (adults), WISC-V (children), ADOS-2 (autism diagnosis), ABAS-II (adaptive behaviour), Merrill-Palmer-R (early development).
- e) Parental questionnaires: SCQ, RBS-R, SRS-2, ABC-C, SDQ, BEARS, sensory profile, AQ (parents), EQ-5D-5L (participant, mother and father quality of life).

Activity	Data type	Legislation	Objective	From	Minimum time	Recommended time	Action at recommended time	Exceptions to elimination / cancelation / anonymization
Research	Genomic data	Ley de investigación	Genetic analysis to detect genomic	Project onset; January 2026	End of the project; December 2027	End of the project; December 2027	Elimination	N/A – In case of need for medical purposes,

		biomédica (Spain) GDPR (EU) LOPDGDD (Spain) EHDSR (EU)	alterations related to ASD						the original copy may be recovered
Research	Sociodemographic data	GDPR (EU) LOPDGDD (Spain)	Perform a multivariate analysis to detect factors influencing the course of ASD	Project onset; January 2026	End of the project; December 2027	End of the project; December 2027	Pseudonymation	N/A	
Research	Clinical data	Ley de investigación biomédica (Spain) GDPR (EU) LOPDGDD (Spain) EHDSR (EU) Ley de autonomía de los pacientes (Spain) Ley general de sanidad (Spain)	Perform a multivariate analysis to detect factors influencing the course of ASD	Project onset; January 2026	End of the project; December 2027	End of the project; December 2027	Pseudonymation	N/A	

2. Metadata and documentation accompanying the data.

- Cohort characterization - including cohort structure, demographics of the cases, inclusion and exclusion criteria, diagnosis status.
- Glossary – including file names and description.
- Description of the bioinformatic tool – including a GitHub repository linked to metadata in ZENODO.
- Description of HPC resources – including storage and hours of computational time.
- Data Management Plan – including different versions produced over the course of the project under an open license. Under CC BY 4.0 open license.

3. Data storage and back-up

Data is property of the Genomics Medicine Unit of Navarrabiomed.

Genomic data is stored in NASERTIC, the Data Centre of the Government of Navarra. This platform adheres to strict security measures and the genomic data is protected by multiple security layers. The Firewall displays a double layer from different suppliers. The security of the stored and newly generated data complies with the requirements of the National Security Scheme and the OCDE recommendations for risk management of digital security.

Data analyses is also performed in a computational cluster within NASERTIC. A specific Trusted Research Environment (TRE) was created for the project.

Original genomic data is stored, backed up and managed in the same Data Centre, although independently from our data. A copy of the necessary files was transferred to our TRE, so there isn't a risk of permanently losing data. Thus, we do not plan to routinely backup data. The copy of the genomic files will be deleted at the end of the project, while the generated data will be stored locally at the Genomics Medicine Unit of Navarrabiomed (within a protected network managed and audited by the Government of Navarra). Sociodemographic and clinical data will also be stored locally at the Genomics Medicine Unit of Navarrabiomed (leader of the project).

4. Personal data processing

We use sensitive data. Genomic data can be used for re-identification of a person unequivocally. Moreover, we combine genetic information with sociodemographic and clinical data. To mitigate the risk, personal ID data was dissociated from other information, thus, the research team only works with pseudonymised genomic, demographic and phenotypic/clinical data. We do not need to contact the patient. Only the Principal Investigators of NAGENpediatrics (Dra. Josune Hualde Olascoaga – Pediatrics Service HUN and Dra. Nerea Gorriá Redondo – Neuropediatrics Service HUN) safeguard decoding files. They are also the reference practitioners of the patients whose data were used. Therefore, results will be delivered only to these clinicians for them to consider the most appropriate clinical management.

Personal data treatment follows the requirements of the Reglamento General de Protección de datos (RGPD-Reglamento (UE) 2016/679, LOPGDD 3/2018) and the EHDS regulations.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

Raw genomic data will not be shared or deposited in a repository at any point since it is sensitive data. The results regarding the details and the performance of the tool and the clinical findings will be shared in a research article published in an indexed scientific journal under open licenses,

always preserving personal data protection and personal identities. Prevalence of these disorders may be extremely low, so further permissions will be obtained if data shown in the publication may be enough to identify individuals.

Potentially, raw data may be accessible for re-use via NAGENdata platform upon request provided scientific and ethical approval be in place. Although this option is currently unavailable.

Code and specific information about the bioinformatic tool will be deposited in a repository (e.g. GitHub) and shared via a scientific publication.

Metadata will be deposited in an appropriate repository, such as ZENODO or similar, and linked to a persistent identifier. We will provide sufficient metadata to assure reusability and reproducibility of the tool, albeit input data will not be shared.

Personal data will not be transferred outside the institution.

6. Data management / FAIR

As mentioned above, NAGENdata will safeguard the original genomic and phenotypical data of all the participants included in this project. Any potential data discovery and access should be arranged via those responsible of that project. In this platform, FAIR data objects include the data files, a persistent unique identifier and a description of the standards and formats used.